
USE AND APPLICATION OF ICT AND WEB-TECHNOLOGIES IN LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

The effectiveness Library services by information resources and services to its users. They are also made use of to generate, collect and administer information. ICT is a force that has changed many aspects of the way we live. Libraries using ICT based resources and services to satisfy the easily information needs of their users. The changes brought about by new information & communication technologies have a key effect on the users, work and play web. As more libraries mostly providing in making use of electronic information resources.

Keywords: *ICT, Libraries, resources, Web, Electronics, Reference Services.*

Introduction:

Information & Communication Technology are referred to as the varied collection of technological resources. Today in the era of information technology use of the web technology. The origin of internet and the development of world wide web the information communication, consist of the hardware, software, networks and storage, processing transmission and presentation of information Technology are changing the accessibility of information Libraries to the needs of the users. From traditional online services to today web based services. Digital services, Internet Library Services with similar meanings.

Definition:

ICT stands for “Information communication Technology”. It refers to technologies that provide access to information through telecommunication. It is same as Information Technology (IT), but focuses primary on communication technologies. This includes the internet, wireless network, cell phone and other communication mediums or when computer technology and

telecommunication technology combines together called information communication Technology.

Some of the commonly used web based library services are library webpage,

web OPAC, Bulletin Board Services, Ask-a-Librarian Services, Web forms, digital references services, online document delivery, interlibrary loan, Online help and information skill tutorials, online current awareness bulletins, e-mails based services.

Impact of ICT web Technologies Web 2.0 technologies are very popular with user and many of these tools are an integrated part of their lives. Web 2.0 tools such as social networks, wikis, photo, image, networks, RSS feeds require user to produce information. Use of ICT in

libraries enhances user satisfaction. It provides numerous benefits of library services to users.

Provide speedy and easy access to information, increasingly more user friendly end users.

Advantages of using ICT in the Library:

- Speedy and easy access of Information
- Helps to attract the users.
- More up to data information
- Access to unlimited information from different sources.
- Information flexibility to the users
- Spare the time of the users.
- Increase efficiency
- Increase the range of services offered.
- ICT makes library work easier, faster, cheaper and more effective.
- Improves the quality of library services
- Improve the communication facilities more stable.

Blogs:

Blogs are “Web blogs” or web sites

that allows users to post information by data.

Social Networks:

Social Networks are online networks of individuals or groups connected through common interests, ideas, goals, values or organizations.

Wikis:

Wikis are web pages on which anyone can add content and / or edit

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information. Wikis used properly can be used help users inquire contribute and collaborate all part of the information standards.

Streaming Audio:

Sharing audio files is an easy and quick way for users to create and disseminate information to others with a variety of formats available and free recorders available online, these resources can help users develop writing, listing and speaking skill.

Web & ICT technology used on the Library, Online resources, Access download, print or store data, meta data, OPAC, Access online information, search engine Hands on Internet training, search and retrieval, more services like Libraries.

Recent technology and accomplishment on ICT have been major role opportunities. The digital library movement is rapidly increasing and the traditional libraries are now on their way to digitations with the prelude of ICT application in libraries.

Information Technology has broken the worldwide boundaries, new apparatus and methods help to provide better services to users.

Conclusion:

The ability to view information in its widest context, to determine needs and then locate, evaluate, organize and apply it are key skills. ICT & web application easily use the libraries users. Spare time users. Users need to know how to evaluate text, images, videos, blogs for their accuracy reliability and validity as information sources.

Users are taking advantages of library services. It has become popular, easy and in inexpensive web & ICT application use of Libraries.

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